

AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE PROBLEM-SOLVING CAPACITIES OF PRESERVICE POST-PRIMARY MATHEMATICS TEACHERS: IMPLEMENTATION OF TAUGHT STRATEGIES

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In this study, we report on the ability of nine pre-service post-primary mathematics teachers on a concurrent, initial teacher education programme in an Irish university to apply the 'Rubric Writing' approach to solving mathematical problems of (Mason, Burton, & Stacey, 2011). The conceptual framework of the study draws on (Chapman, 2015), who identifies different characteristics that underpin the effective teaching of mathematical problem-solving. Included here is the capacity to solve problems effectively. The participants in the study had previously received instruction on problem-solving in a formal university module, focussing on the 'Rubric Writing' approach. Each participant undertook two mathematical problems in a 'Think Aloud' manner in recorded interviews. The interviews were then analysed for evidence of implementation of the 'Entry' phase of this approach. We report on this analysis and on how it will be embedded in the ongoing research project.

PROBLEM SOLVING AND TEACHERS OF PROBLEM SOLVING

Mathematical problem solving occupies a privileged position in the Irish post-primary mathematics syllabus. Problem solving is identified as one of the six elements of the Unifying Strand of the Junior Cycle syllabus that over-arches the four content strands (Number, Geometry & Trigonometry, Algebra & Functions, Statistics & Probability). Likewise, mathematical problem solving is highlighted under the 'Being Numerate' heading of the Junior Cycle Key Skills, and constitutes one of the 24 'Statements of Learning' of the Junior Cycle (NCCA, 2017). So mathematical problem solving is recognized and valued as a central part of post-primary mathematics education, nationally and internationally (Conway & Sloane, 2005).

According to Kilpatrick (1985), while problems have held a fundamental role in the school mathematics curriculum, problem solving has not. Kilpatrick comments that with the focus on the idea of developing problem solving skills, there is confusion regarding the actual definition of problem solving. Indeed, Schoenfeld (1992) identifies that there are various meanings for the terms "problems" and "problem solving": see also (Lester, 2013). Nowhere is this lack of agreement clearer than in the work of Chamberlin (2008). In this study, Chamberlin applied a Delphi technique protocol (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2007, p.309) to attempt "to ascertain what mathematical problem solving is in the primary and secondary mathematics classroom" (Chamberlin, 2008, p. 1). After three rounds of analysis, a group of twenty participants (experts on mathematical problem-solving in the classroom) reached consensus on just 21 of 38 statements on the relevance of certain issues to the components and characteristics of problem solving. This lack of consensus must be set against the widespread acknowledgement of the importance of problem solving in the mathematics curriculum (Conway & Sloane, 2005).

In recognition for the need for clarity of our use of the phrase *mathematical problem solving*, we will highlight three items. Firstly, Lester (2013) notes that among the many different perspectives on problem solving, there appears to be agreement that there must be a goal, a problem solver and the lack of a means of immediately attaining the goal. Next, we consider the role of problem solving within the statement of key learning outcomes as presented in the NCCA syllabus document:

Students should be able to investigate patterns, formulate conjectures, and engage in tasks in which the solution is not immediately obvious, in familiar and unfamiliar contexts (NCCA, 2017, p.10).

Finally, we mention the characterization offered in (Lester & Kehle, 2003):

Successful problem solving involves coordinating previous experiences, knowledge, familiar representations and patterns of inference, and intuition in an effort to generate new representations and related patterns of inference that resolve some tension or ambiguity (i.e., lack of meaningful representations and supporting inferential moves) that prompted the original problem-solving activity (Lester & Kehle, 2003, p.510).

This third characterization includes the key elements of problem solving that are the focus of the larger research project of which this study is a part. The problems and problem solving activities of this project reflect the three items noted above. The project in question addresses the development of capacities for teaching problem solving among pre-service, post-primary mathematics teachers (we discuss this in more detail below). A key concern is the question of what these capacities are. That is; what do mathematics teachers need to know, what skills do they need to have, and what are the attitudes that they should hold in order to be effective teachers of mathematical problem solving? The question of how to prepare teachers for the task of teaching problem solving has attracted much attention. Chapman (2015) discusses six capacities that teachers need in order to teach problem solving effectively:

Knowledge of problems

This describes the teacher's ability to select and design mathematical problems. Chapman maintains that when selecting problems, the teacher must be aware of the potential impact of the characteristics of the problems on their students. For example, Silver and Thompson (1984) show that students experience greater difficulty with multistep problems than one-step problems. Other researchers find that secondary school students find abstract problems considerably more difficult than concrete problems (Caldwell & Goldin, 1987), and that students have difficulty in understanding the text of a word problem more than the actual solution (Lewis & Mayer, 1987).

Knowledge of problem solving

Teachers should be proficient in problem solving and in understanding the nature of approaches to problem solving. Chapman (2015) outlines that teachers' own proficiency in problem solving is essential for them to be able to understand students' approaches and predict the implications of these approaches. The teachers' proficiency also underpins their ability to decipher students' unusual solutions, whether or not these will be beneficial, and

what makes them so. Problem solving proficiency is also needed so that the teachers may make connections between the mathematics in different solutions for the same problem and the mathematics among different problems. Chapman (2015) suggests that to teach for problem solving proficiency, the teacher must be aware of the many problem solving models that exist and understand the thinking that must occur during the process to achieve a solution.

Knowledge of Problem Posing

This capacity includes a teacher's ability to generate new problems and to adapt existing problems for their students' needs. It is important for teachers to have this skill as it can have a positive influence on students' mathematical thinking and therefore improve their problem solving ability (English, 1997, cited in Chapman, 2015). Chapman outlines findings by Silver, Mamona-Downs, Leung and Kenney (1996) which found that both practicing and preservice teachers created problems that were either predictable, undemanding, ill-formulated or unsolvable, when trying to make expansions on given problems.

Knowledge of students as problem solvers

Chapman notes that this is important for the teacher to have to help improve students' problem solving proficiency. Chapman advises that teachers should be aware of the characteristics of 'good' problem solvers and the heuristics employed and dispositions of these solvers to help them promote these behaviours in their students.

Knowledge of problem solving instruction

This is a trait that is vital for teachers to have to teach for problem solving proficiency. Chapman outlines the drawbacks of showing the students a method and then the students practising similar methods compared to the advantages of the teacher employing a constructivist role in the classroom (Kilpatrick, 1985).

Affective Factors and Beliefs

These could both impact students' problem solving. Chapman refers to Polya (1962) who stated the importance of a teachers' positive attitude in aiding students in problem solving. The understanding of the students' own beliefs is required by the teacher and the teacher must try to develop the students'; belief in their ability, appreciation of understanding concepts, the necessity of word problems as part of mathematics, and a belief that effort will improve their mathematical ability (Kloosterman & Stage, 1992).

THE STUDY

Participants and Mason's Rubric Writing

The participants in this study are pre-service mathematics teachers (PSMTs) undertaking a concurrent initial teacher education programme. Graduates of the relevant programmes typically go on to careers teaching mathematics in Ireland, and so preparing the PSMTs for the task of teaching problem solving is a key concern of the programme team. Participants are drawn from two cohorts of students, both of whom were taking a module that includes the study (and practice) of mathematical problem solving. The participants all went through the Leaving Certificate mathematics curriculum and had reduced exposure to problems since

there is a lack of problems in Leaving Certificate textbooks (O’Sullivan, 2017). Along with this there is not a high mathematics entry requirement for either programme from which the participants were drawn. Thus, it is possible to classify the participants as novice problem solvers which implies that structured approaches are useful in their solving of problems (Schoenfeld, 1992). This module adopted the Rubric Writing approach to problem solving (Mason et al., 2011). The participants in the study were introduced to this approach in a series of 10 lectures and 8 workshops. These provided instruction in applying Rubric Writing, supported by worked examples of problem solving, and with the opportunity to apply the technique to unseen problems taken from (Mason et al., 2011). This Rubric Writing approach (which may be described as a problem-solving heuristic) provides structured guidelines to promote the introduction of diagrams and notation, to draw upon prior knowledge, and focus on metacognition through the reviewing of work.

The present study focusses knowledge of problem solving as described above. We focussed on their problem-solving proficiency: “*what is necessary for one to learn and do genuine problem solving successfully*” (Chapman, 2015, p.20). In particular, we examine the students’ capacity to use the *Entry Phase* of Mason’s rubric writing approach. Mason et al. (2011) define the *Entry Phase* as beginning when first encountering the question and ending when the problem-solver is involved in attempting to solve the problem. They note the importance of this phase in progressing and ultimately succeeding in finding a solution. They state that without satisfactory entry to a problem, the next phase, the *Attack Phase*, cannot come about. Mason et al. outline that since the *Entry Phase* is important for the preparation of a successful *Attack Phase*, it is crucial to dedicate sufficient time to it. To create an effective *Entry Phase*, Mason et al. suggest the inclusion of the following three questions in the problem-solvers’ rubric writing; *What do I know?*, *What do I want?*, and *What can I introduce?*

Methodology

Participants were volunteers from the cohorts undertaking the module mentioned above (this group comprised a total of 40 students). Nine students participated in the study. They were provided with information relating to data protection, with a plain language description of the project and with a consent form explicitly offering the opportunity to opt out of the study at any stage. The PSMTs were interviewed on a one-on-one basis by one of the researchers (EO). They were given two problems: Problem One dealing with probability and Problem Two with geometry and trigonometry. Both problems were taken from the NRICH website (NRICH, 2019) where the problems are organised by age categories with the difficulty of the problems measured on a scale of 1-3 stars (3 stars being most difficult). Problem One is classified as a 2-star short probability problem appropriate for students age 14-16. Problem Two is classified as a 3-star short trigonometry problem appropriate for students aged 14-16. The participants were asked to solve the problems following a ‘Think Aloud’ protocol (Salkind, 2010). While the ‘Think Aloud’ method may alter the participants’ problem-solving approach due to the environment it is a method which is widely used in education research to gather data on working memory of participants (Charters, 2003). Interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed. The interviews ranged in duration from 04:54 to 31.36 minutes. The written work produced by the PSMTs during the protocol was retained for analysis.

Data Analysis

The interview transcripts have been analysed in two different ways. An approach based on the general inductive analysis of Thomas (2006) has been reported on elsewhere (Owens & Nolan, 2019). We report here on the second approach, where we rated the combined interview data and written work in terms of the degree to which these evidenced implementation of the Rubric Writing approach of Mason et al., (2011). This was done by both researchers independently and then compared and revised as necessary. To identify evidence of applying the *Entry Phase* we used the following characterizations (Mason et al., (2011)):

Mason describes '*I Want*' as directing attention to the task at hand or deciding what is needed to be done in order to solve the problem. Evidence that we looked for was that the participant (re)stated precisely the goal of the problem (the value of a positive integer N in Problem 1, and the value of a distance x in Problem 2). '*I Know*' refers to selecting all the relevant information given in the problem and identifying any associated mathematical concepts that are likely to be relevant. For this study, we looked for evidence of *I Know* early on in the attempt where the participant recorded relevant information given in the problem and or stating related mathematical facts. '*Introduce*' includes the introduction of notation, organizing the *I Know* elements, and representing information in the question through the use of tables, charts, and diagrams. Evidence of *Introduce* in this study was identified as the drawing of diagrams, the introduction of notation, and constructions within the given diagram in Problem 2.

RESULTS

The analysis of the *Entry Phase* of Mason's Rubric Writing Approach was done by implementing the following grading system; 0 points (no evidence); 1 point (limited evidence); 2 points (strong evidence). This grading was carried out for both questions for each of the nine participants and for each of the three elements of the *Entry Phase* namely, *Introduce*, *I Know*, and *I Want*. This generated 54 data items. Both researchers rated the interview transcripts separately and initially agreed on the scoring of 42 of the 54 items (78%). For the remaining 12 items, the scores differed by at most one point. No disagreements remained following a discussion. Table 1 summarises the grading of the *Entry Phase* for both problems.

Table 1: Entry Phase count for the cohort for both problems.

Problem One		
<i>Introduce</i>	<i>Want</i>	<i>Know</i>
0	8	9
Problem Two		
Introduce	Want	Know
10	6	9

Examples that were categorized as participants' use of the *Entry Phase* are given below.

Introduce

Question 2 included a diagram, but many participants opted to redraw it themselves:

P9: “I’ll draw it out in front of me so there’s the well, so I have 5, 10 and x”.

Within this category, extensions of given diagrams or constructions based on them also feature, as did diagrams drawn multiple times and with different sizes. Participants also drew diagrams with the view to then manipulating them:

P8: “I’m going to draw them down and make right angled triangles”,

P6: “We could make a right angle here...OK so I’ll draw it”.

Participants also introduced notation which is acknowledged by both Polya (1962) and Mason et al., (2011) as a feature that frequently underpins successful problem solving. Examples of notation include labelling angles or sides (P8):

P8: “I’m just drawing...five Y plus P” ... “The sides so that’s A and that’s B”.

I Know and I Want

Statements in these categories scored as +1 or +2 only when they clearly appeared in the *Entry Phase* of the problem solving activity – prior to the *Attack Phase*. Many such statements involved students repeating or highlighting the information given in the problem. This is discussed as being important in Mason et al. (2011), and was emphasized during instruction. In some cases, there were instances of *I Want* and *I Know* statements being made *after* the *Entry Phase* of the problem. For example, when Participant 1 got stuck, they then went back and stated what he knows and wants but these were more of a rationale for the approach and work that he did, rather than used as a starting point. Many of the participants jumped straight into an approach without stating what they know about the problem from the information given or stating what they want to find. Participant 5 was an example of this whereby they did not demonstrate any of the *Entry Phase* and specialized straight away.

Some participants excluded different approaches based on their ‘*I know*’ statements. For example, Participant 9 stated that they do not have adequate information to use either the Sine Rule or the Cosine rule. This demonstrates that they know that both of these approaches are applicable to triangles, and also know what is required to use them.

Stating what ‘I know’ or ‘I want’ sometimes led participants to an ‘Introduce’ element:

P7: “I was going to try and do Pythagoras...try and turn one of the triangles into a right-angled triangle by drawing a straight line from the well to the side”.

Similarly, Participant 4 states that they know that Pythagoras is only for right-angled triangle and introduced lines breaking up the given triangles into right-angled triangles. Both at the beginning of the attempt and throughout, Participant 4 repeatedly questioned themselves:

P4: “What else do I know?”.

Although participants made statements in relation to the three components of the *Entry Phase*, none of them wrote down explicitly ‘*I know*’ or ‘*I want*’ as they had been advised.

CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The interview protocol described allowed us to study PSMTs' implementation of Mason's Rubric Writing approach. The use of the *Introduce* component of the *Entry Phase* was the most commonly used element, particularly in Problem Two. This problem, although given with a diagram, required *Introduce* to solve the problem. For example, in one approach, right-angled triangles and rectangles need to be constructed to solve the problem. This was done to various degrees by several of the participants. However, such were wholly absent in relation to Problem 1 (see Table 1) – where only one student successfully solved the problem.

Our reading of the data is that none of the participants explicitly and purposefully implemented Mason's Rubric Writing approach. No student showed evidence of implementing each of the three elements of the *Entry Phase*, and of the 54 items, only 8 scored a maximum of 2 points. This indicates that continued review of the current module is needed. Despite lectures and practical tutorials emphasizing the effectiveness of Mason's Rubric Writing approach, there was a clear lack of application of it. This is concerning as the participants are not deemed to be expert problem solvers and should therefore rely on a guided approach such as Mason's Rubric Writing when stuck in a problem. An encouraging feature was that although none of the participants wrote down the components of the *Entry Phase*, there were verbal referrals to them. There were many examples of the participants introducing diagrams, stating information that they knew to help them progress or get a starting point, and some participants stated what they were looking for after reading the problem.

Although the number of participants is small [N=9], we see implications for our work with PSMTs in developing their problem solving capacities, recognising this as a central part of their formation as teachers of mathematical problem solving (Chapman, 2015). Deeper engagement over a longer duration is indicated to improve problem-solving proficiency in prospective teachers. Future research work will focus on the other elements of Chapman's framework along with a revised repetition of this study (Chapman, 2015).

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